

USE OF MODERN PEDAGOGICAL AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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Abstract. Teaching English has become one of the most pressing issues on the world stage today. Because English is recognized as the number one international language in the world. This article details the modern information technologies used in English language teaching.

Keywords: foreign language, teaching technology, modern technology, educator, student, reading and learning skills, etc.

Today, the importance of learning English in Uzbekistan is much higher than before. A number of English language experts are implementing new methods and ways of learning English. This, of course, increases the effectiveness of foreign language teaching. There are several benefits to using technology in teaching. In addition, it significantly increases the effectiveness of the teaching system and, in turn, helps the language learner to keep pace with the times and move forward. Technology is slowly replacing traditional teaching. Today, a number of new programs and shows are being aired on television programs to help teach English.

The fact that some teachers do not know and do not use technology during English lessons leads to some boredom of students. That is why the use of technology and at least a computer in the classroom to keep the learner motivated increases the learner's interest. After all, the training materials, prepared depending on the age, interests, abilities, mastery of the lessons, will be effective. Conversely, if we teachers do not select teaching materials based on these requirements, we will not be able to provide primary school students with videos, songs, or texts that contain complex words, or if they will be shown on multimedia computers. When we demonstrate very simple texts to middle and high school or group learners, learners' interest in learning the language gradually begins to wane and they stop

learning. This, in turn, can lead to lower grades and a teacher's loss of self-esteem in the eyes of students. Therefore, the main task is not only the use of technology in the classroom, but also to ensure that they can be used in their proper place and that the use of technology serves to increase student knowledge. According to the current CEFR, the requirements of the International European Educational Standards are four: (writing, reading, listening, speaking) competencies in writing, reading, listening and speaking in English. It is important to use technology effectively and appropriately during lessons. For example, there are rules for listening to audio texts. It is important that the main goal is for the learner to understand the audio material he or she is listening to and to be able to analyze it without difficulty. To do this, first of all, prepare the environment for the release of audio material, so that the listeners have a quiet environment, and the teacher pays attention to the quality of the audio and the performance of the amplifiers, and exercises before and after the audio. and learners should be provided with handouts. Once all the requirements have been met, the teacher can begin to broadcast the audio material to the learners. Broadcasting is done at least twice, otherwise language learners may not understand the topic and may not be able to perform the exercises correctly after listening to the audio material.

It is also a very effective way to show and discuss video-films, videos, using multimedia in the teaching and learning process using technology in conversation and writing. It is possible to use a dictionary familiar to learners, to explain words if new and complex words are involved, to show a video after completing exercises related to new words. In order to carry out this process, it is important to have a quiet, quiet environment, a comfortable and clean classroom, access to public viewing, and check that the amplifiers are working. Before releasing the video, the learners should discuss the topic of the video that needs to be demonstrated, conduct a Q&A session, and release the video material after making sure that the learners are really interested in the topic. When the video is over, the teacher will be interested in the students' ideas about the video film and will do exercises. When these steps are done correctly, these lessons will certainly contribute to the growth of students' interest and knowledge. Therefore, the role of modern technologies in further

enriching our lessons, attracting students, enriching their knowledge is invaluable. Proper and appropriate application of them is the main guarantee of our success. In this process, including:

- when using computers, the student can watch and listen to videos, demonstrations, dialogues, movies or cartoons in a foreign language;
- It is possible to listen and watch radio broadcasts in foreign languages and TV programs; - use of tape recorders and cassettes, which are more traditional methods;
- CD players are available. The use of these tools makes the process of learning a foreign language more interesting and effective for students.

Today, interactive games are becoming a tradition in schools. It is well known that a variety of play-based activities help students demonstrate their abilities, focus, increase their knowledge and skills, and become stronger. We know that in the current educational process, the student has to be a subject. Focusing on more interactive methods will increase learning effectiveness. One of the most important requirements for English lessons is to teach students to think independently. Today, English teachers use the following innovative methods, based on the experience of United States states and English educators:

- “Creative Problem Solving” is the beginning of the story. students are referred to the student judgment;
- “Merry Riddles” Teaching riddles to students is important in teaching English, they learn words they are unfamiliar with and find the answer to a riddle;
- Quick answers help to increase the effectiveness of the lesson;
- “Warm-up exercises” to use a variety of games in the classroom to engage students in the lesson;
- Pantomime can be used in a class where very difficult topics need to be explained, or when students are tired of writing exercises;
- A chain story method helps to develop students' oral skills;

- Acting characters This method can be used in all types of lessons. Professionals such as Translator, Writer, and Poet can participate in the class and talk to students;
- Poets and writers such as U. Shakespeare, A. Navoi, R. Burns can be "invited". At the same time, using the words of wisdom they say in class will help young people grow up to be perfect people;
- The “When pictures speak” method is more convenient and helps to teach English, to develop students' oral speech, it is necessary to use thematic pictures;
- Quiz cards are distributed according to the number of students and allow all students to attend classes at the same time, which saves time.

As we have seen, each innovative technology has its own set of advantages. All of these methods involve collaboration between teacher and student, active participation of the student in the educational process. In short, the use of innovative methods in English lessons develops students' logical thinking skills, fluency, and the ability to respond quickly and accurately. Such methods stimulate the student's desire for knowledge. The student tries to prepare well for the lessons. This makes students active participants in the learning process. As the education system sets itself the task of nurturing a free-thinking, well-rounded, mature person, in the future we will contribute to the further development of effective use of innovative technologies by future teachers.

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